

“EXTEND” to the “NEXT LEVEL”

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Abstract

EXTEND is a project that assigned itself the aim of promoting student centred learning in Higher Education engineering institutions (from Russian Federation and Tajikistan) in a technologically enhanced framework by creating a sound pragmatic base i.e. the EXTEND Centres. The process of implementing such an aim requires a huge overhaul and development of a wide range of skills: designing, developing, implementing, managing, evaluating. In all this process, the organized mind has been a key prerequisite every step of the way. As the project deadline is drawing closer, a critical question has been hovering around: *what comes next?* The accompanying concern might be: can the organized mind play the same role in the post-project sustainability stage? What are the factors to be juggled into a new development format? The present paper sums up some of the tentative answers offered to this question in one of the project related workshops as well as considerations that pertain to the field of pedagogic change literature and project management. In an attempt to operationalize the solution, the initial question was changed into two preliminary questions. First: “*what came next*” in similar projects of a developmental nature. Secondly, *what might come next* against the backdrop of the accumulated experiential learning of EXTEND participants and an increasingly pervasive digital culture. Both issues have the same aim in view: long term educational development.

Key words: sustainability, impact, organized mind, serendipity

1 Introduction

EXTEND (2017-2020) is an EU project subtitled **Excellence in Engineering Education through Teacher Training and New Pedagogic Approaches in Russia and Tajikistan (EXTEND 586060-EPP-1-2017-1-RO-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP)** and initiated under the ERASMUS + Programme, KA2, Capacity Building in Higher Education (CBHE). Projects of educational change like EXTEND hold a lot of promise for the future but also challenges. These challenges may become the object of concerns that are both legitimate and welcome at individual and institutional level. Some of these concerns were the object of one particular EXTEND workshop. This workshop was scheduled in the agenda of the EXTEND Dissemination Conference entitled **Development of Engineering Teaching through the New Pedagogy Approaches in Higher Education Institutions of Tajikistan** - 25 June (TNU) – 26 June 2019 (TUT), Dushanbe, Tajikistan. The workshop was delivered by Doina Irina SIMION as a representative of the University Politehnica of Bucharest (UPB), Romania, the institution in charge of the project coordination headed by Elisabeth LAZAROU. The main point of the workshop was to clarify development options the EXTEND participants might consider after the end of the project as an answer to their key question: *what will happen when EXTEND is over?* The present paper – on the one hand- largely draws upon the Dushanbe workshop activities and results. On the other hand, the paper broadens the scope for an answer in two ways. First, by looking into “*what happened*” in the post-project stage in a similar venture targeting long term gains. Secondly, by overviewing ways of ensuring sustainability that go beyond the promises of the organized mind. In other words, the paper looks into “*what might happen*” or “*the next level*”.

2 “What Happened?”

Long term success depends on a variety of factors sometimes not easy to predict. One such example of success was the Romanian-British project entitled PROSPER profiled in Table 1. The project targeted methodological update in the teaching/learning of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) in key Romanian engineering universities in the 1990 decade. The implementation and dissemination of the communicative approach ideology was seen as a benchmark of project success. This success was thoroughly documented in “The PROSPER Project, Innovation in Teaching English for Specific Purposes in Romania, A study of Impact”, 1999. The PROSPER project

experience may be considered relevant on several accounts. First, PROSPER, alike with EXTEND, was a project for change. Secondly, its conclusions map out the key features which in Donald Freeman's opinion (1989) characterize *any* teaching situation: *teacher knowledge, skill, attitude* and *awareness*. Furthermore, although EXTEND is not confined to language teaching, it does include a language training component in the Module developed by NMSTU on Foreign Languages for Engineering and Academic Writing. Down below is a selective choice of post-PROSPER spinoffs encountered at the level of *the teacher, the context, methodology* which might be considered a wake up call for EXTEND practitioners.

2.1 The Teacher as Learner

Educational change involves a complex software and hardware infrastructure: ideas, materials, activities. For the teacher open to change, the first contact with this new world is through language. Freema Elbaz makes an impactful analysis of the relation between language, the action capable of changing existing reality and power.

'language provides the conceptual categories which organize thought into predetermined patterns and set the boundaries of discourse' (Bowers 1987: 116 apud Elbaz, 1991, p.1). The ability to determine these conceptual categories constitutes power. As researchers we exercise such power; hence it is important to consider the categories in which research in our field has been organized, and to ask where these categories come from and what part of reality and whose reality they reflect (Freema Elbaz, 1991, p.1).

In tune with this approach, a micro-research in the professional environment of the English Department UPB staffers involved in the PROSPER¹ Project found that the scientific jargon of the communicative approach methodology had been in the beginning stage of the project a steady source of stress. A questionnaire based survey revealed the following items as being particularly sensitive: *input, output, realia, task, monitoring, peer, pair, teacher fronted, lock step, follow up*. It is easy to see that most of them are not so much institution related but rather teacher related. They concern the teacher's role (*teacher fronted, lock step*, with mostly the negative connotations of "the old school" or *monitoring, follow up* with the positive connotations of the "new school"); interactivity (*peer, pair*), or the learning by doing methodology (*input, output, realia, follow up*) (Simion, 2006).

The EXTEND project is open to a wide range of fields and subjects in Engineering Education. Consequently, the scientific jargon used is bound to vary too. However, the weight of educational jargon in a paradigm of educational change is probably comparable across fields. That is why being aware of the importance of assimilating the meta-language of change in a hands-on type of learning experience might or even should be embedded in the kind of materials, activities, decision making required in the post-EXTEND history. The key pre-requisites being: conceptual clarity, time for assimilation, meaningfulness of use.

2.2 The Context

In his seminal work *Changing Teachers, Changing Times* (1995) Andrew Hargreaves identified five types of work context for an educationalist: fragmented individualism, balkanization, collaborative culture, imposed collegiality, mobile mosaic. Individualism is defined by an attitude of isolation and defensiveness towards external interventions. Balkanization is defined by group related loyalties and lack of consistency; the collaborative culture context moves toward trust and mutual help relationships that may however face the risk of paternalism. The context of imposed collegiality features collaboration relationships induced and controlled by senior leadership via administrative measures; this kind of context poses no risks but engenders no novelty either. In the mobile mosaic work environment Group members carry out different functions by rotation which result in the emergence of dynamic, flexible groups despite the risk of uncertainty and vulnerability.

The DUSHANBE workshop took place at the end of the second year of the EXTEND project. It offered participants the possibility to assess the quality of their present professional environment by asking them the question: What kind of environment do you consider you are living in at present? (use Hargreaves' taxonomy). The results of the survey showed on the one hand a reluctance of considering the issue (46% no answers) as well as an awareness of the emergence of collaborative types, i.e. 33% *collaborative*, 13% *Imposed collegiality*,

0.66%, *moving mosaic*. Although no in-depth investigation was carried out into the reason for non-response, one might assume that participants were either uneasy about assigning an inferior label to their present work environment or considered the very issue superfluous. These results are a signal that the quality of the work environment might prove critical for the sustainability of the EXTEND project in the future. The educational milieu of EXTEND has already become sensitized to context related issues by the participatory research involved in drafting the survey dedicated to the question “What is Good Teaching” (Outcome 1.1).

2.3 Methodology - from lock step to empowerment

The lock-step methodology to most Romanian engineering students of foreign languages were subjected before the introduction of the communicative approach is succinctly drawn up in the baseline study undertaken as part of the PROSPER Project. Here are some key findings regarding the main stakeholders, the teachers and the students.

The PRE-PROSPER teacher tended to be domineering in class, assuming the entire responsibility for the class and consequently allowing little opportunity for students to learn through contributing actively in class. The teacher-student relationship was generally good but some teachers were too rigorous and demanding, very strict on errors, intimidating students, as they offered no encouragement or possibility of self/peer correction. Very often only the students with a higher knowledge of English were involved by the teacher in class activities.

Other important findings refer to: lack of clear lesson objectives and coherent pattern off classroom activities; heavy focus on grammar and accuracy, little emphasis on the four skills training; too much talking time about the language rather than opportunities for using it purposefully, in a contextualised, product based frame; unbalanced lessons in terms of teacher input and student output with a heavy stress on teacher input. (Source: The PROSPER Project, Innovation in Teaching English for Specific Purposes in Romania, A study of Impact, 1999, p. 24).

As to students, the baseline study found-in the wake of 30 observation classes carried out in 1991-1992- that they were “not very motivated, behaving as passive recipients, used to being told what to do”, (*op.cit.* p. 66).’ often diligently writing things down, even when it was extremely boring’, ‘poor at asking questions’, not familiar with pair work or group work.

In the wake of almost ten years of intensive investment in methodological training, the same study documented a change in the above situation both with respect to teachers as well as students. The key areas of teacher development were found in six directions: teacher-student relationship, better teaching skills, development of materials writing skills, provision of more opportunities for students to communicate, increased co-operation with colleagues (*op.cit.* p. 41). The student profile also changed in terms of the “learning experience, /.../ types of activities and patterns of classroom interaction, access to materials, and teacher-student relationship” (*op.cit.* p. 89).

The EXTEND Centres and the PROSPER Language Centres are both conceived as agents of educational change through a learner centred, humanized teaching methodology. The list of PROSPER activities and outcomes in Annex 1 is indicative of the kind of resources needed to successfully implement this goal.

3 The next level

In simple terms, project sustainability means building up and capitalizing on the project gains – after the fund flow has stopped - via such means like commercialisation, accreditation or mainstreaming. The above mentioned Impact study is good proof that educational change is both possible and sustainable. As far as the sustainability of the EXTEND Project is concerned, the project design has already provided for it. The third draft of the sustainability plan (last updated in March 2020) is a convincing example of what the “organized mind” can achieve. The plan overviews the exploitation strategy, tools, target audience, description of events and overall exploitation calendar in the post EXTEND stage. Furthermore, the plan makes a fine point of realistic philosophy by stating that “Not all parts of the project or results may be sustainable”. Indeed, success is not a matter of push-button performance.

Nevertheless, beyond what the “organized mind” can forecast, there lies the land of practice. Donald Schon (1987) once stated that this land always poses a challenge because problems rarely have black and white answers, the answers lie in a sort of “grey”, “marshy” area. That is the reason why any sustainability plan should not overlook one of the most important factors of change: the *quality* of the human factor. Here is a list of some of the issues that might challenge the human factor as an agent of change in the post-EXTEND stage. They stem from both theoretical and (auctorial) experiential insights.

The Ground. Antoinette Oberg (1989) has put forth a very important concept that accounts for the teacher’s ability to face the changing educational reality: the ground of practice. The author claims that even before a teacher steps into the room she/he is equipped with a mental and emotional cast that informs current decision making. This entity expresses the individual practitioner’s outlook on the “educational good”, is multi-dimensional, complex, abstract, developing, personal, partially comprehensible and accessible only in specific instances (Oberg, 1989). The components of this complex entity are the practitioner’s beliefs and intentions as well as the links between them and eventually, actions. Similarly, the EXTEND practitioner is also likely to impact her/his practice in a more or less conscious way with the values of the humanized approach to education promoted by EXTEND, as part of her/his new ground of practice.

Support. Change theorists have also emphasized the importance of steady support after a certain skill or technique has been assimilated. Support – as shared goals and tasks- may be provided at peer or group level. The ten year deployment and success of the PROSPER project is good proof of this finding. In the case of the UPB English Department for instance, the project investment spawned a range of initiatives, i.e., developing in-house text-books (i.e. *English for Professional Communication*, 2004), a testing team as well as other collaborative ventures. The bad news is that when support is deficient, work quality runs the risk of falling to levels that go even lower than the pre-change levels. So, one piece of warning might be: beware of isolation!

Self-monitoring. There is no universally agreed classification of the stages in the development of an educational practitioner. Day (1993) sums them up to three: launching, stabilization and experimentation. Kenneth Leithwood added a fourth one, the plateau stage, which may have either positive features, i.e. a heightened moral sense of responsibility and lessened competition focus or negative ones, i.e. stagnation and cynicism. These phases might be replicated in the case of a limited experiential exposure such as EXTEND. In other words, the EXTEND participant in the third project year might hold views, might be aware of values, might be capable of implementing educational procedures that were alien to the same participant who attended the EXTEND kick off meeting in 2017 (see Motto at the head of Conclusions). Mention should be made that the experimental stage may lead to diversification, assumption of more responsibilities, revelations or puzzlement (Day, *op.cit*). One possible danger-that might occur when the practitioner lacks adequate support – is over-experimentation for the sake of experimentation. The antidote in this case might be the quality self-monitoring based on reflective practice. Even if keeping professional diaries or any sort of logs was an optional decision for individual EXTEND participants, an overview of the archive of the EXTEND minutes drawn up in the wake of all project milestones might act as a strong reflection booster with both personal and collective benefits.

Imagination (and its off-spring, innovation *per se*), is considered one of the most formidable tools of progress, as Albert Einstein once claimed.

“When I examine myself and my methods of thought ... I come close to the conclusion that the gift of imagination has meant more to me than any talent for absorbing absolute knowledge ... All great achievements of science must start from intuitive knowledge” (Albert Einstein apud Levitin, *The Organized Mind*, p. 381).

Serendipity. Attempts at capitalizing on this basically uncontrollable process which is imagination have led to the increased interest shown in the educational field to serendipity as a rich source for discovery. This latter concept rationalizes the path towards creativity by tapping at the associative power provided by instances of diversity. Nowadays, exposure to diversity for the sake of fortunate findings or discoveries has become a popular technique in online advertising, online search, scientific research (i.e. Stumble Upon – search engine-<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/StumbleUpon>), or entertainment: (i.e. Mood logic music).

Gamification, the transfer of (computer) game principles to other areas contexts promises to provide the interest, implication, learning challenge, and most of all instant feedback which Mihaly Csikszentmihaly (2015) associates with the sources of the state of flow or happiness. Up to now, gamification has found a wide range of applications in education (USA army, Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation 'Quest to Learn'), marketing (tablet game winners), health Industry, whether directly (see the good correlates of gaming elements and health self monitoring applications in Appstore 2014) or indirectly (Pokemon Go, 1500 steps), labour corporate training or public policy making (ex. social credit earned in China for good reputation scores). Nowadays, the most popular gamification inspired activities feature: score points, score tablets, story sequels Avatars, medals performance graphs, team work games; experience levels (RPG role play games). Future EXTEND off-springs can only benefit from capitalizing on this direction of educational methodology.

Feedback. Seen as a prerequisite/ follow-up of any dissemination plan, feedback data may eventually turn out into one of the most reliable sources of self and institutional improvement if pursued in a consistent way.

The old vs. the new rhetoric. THE EXTEND Consortium emerged in the wake of a common determination to implement the upgrading of local educational systems. Success, however, at any stage in the project development- pre-while-post - is most often a matter of context, i.e. rules and people. In the sustainability stage, as far as people – trainers or trainees- are concerned, one should not take for granted either an un-negotiated adoption of the new or a total rejection of the old before clarifying the boundaries of the new and the old. The eight EXTEND Modules that represent a major agent for change in the project design feature state of the art topics (especially ICT related) and incentives for a humanised teaching methodology. Hence, they target both competence and performance. The scope of the novelty impact is not restricted to trainers and trainees but engulfs the broader area of scholarly literature, administrators at various levels or even news media, etc. Nevertheless, the novelty of EXTEND, in the existing environments, should not necessarily be seen as a break-up trigger but rather as a build-up of valuable pre-existing expertise.

That is the reason why one should earnestly consider what the theoretical and pragmatic basis for this build-up might be. In other words: is there any place for the old? If yes, in what respect? And why? The why is easy to answer if we consider the human factor. Educational systems are reputedly reluctant to change, especially imposed top down change. The assumption of change opponents are most often than not the commonsensical outlook summed up under the slogan: if things have worked like that for decades and decades there must have been something good about them. Indeed, if we look at the history of educational practice and theory, we cannot overlook the existence of some perennial pillars which some theorists call "commonplaces".

The concept of a commonplace already received significant attention of quite a few educational theorists. In his "Guide to commonplaces: on the use of *loci* in educators' discourse", Henry Maurice' (1991) lists such contributors to the concept as R. Mc Keon, Kenneth Burke, J. Schwab, E. Eisner. His analysis overviews a variety of more or less surprising interpretations of this concept: J. Schwab collects under the umbrella term of the commonplace the very stock elements of education: the teacher, the learner, the milieu, the subject matter. K. Burke draws up an analogy between communication and education on the basis of such shared "commonplaces" like act, scene, agent, agency or purpose.

The previous references to the concept of commonplace support the theoretical validity of the question" is there any place for the old. Pragmatically, one could look into the transfer value of previous practice. Economy precludes an in-depth analysis of all possible transferable skills. As EXTEND trainers are expected to be experts of teaching, one can refer to the literature on expert teaching in this respect. The way subject/content knowledge and procedural knowledge merge into what is called "pedagogical content knowledge" (Schulman apud Gudmundsdottir, 1991) is a field still open to hypotheses. However, one key assumption is that teachers work out an individual, mostly thematic narrative that links up the key topics of their subject into a major idea ort story in order to provide continuity and meaningfulness for their students . It is easy to see that the challenge of developing a background narrative stays valid irrespective of topic or method novelty. The ability to tailor the teaching discourse in a direction likely to foster specialists in a certain field rather than a "fit for all pattern" recipe, or pivoting discourse on the kind of theory that ensures "depth" rather than "breadth" (Duschl, apud Meung, 1991) can also feature transferable values.

The EXTEND post project stage will not be carried out in the void. The future actors and stakeholders should be aware of the critical stakes of a digitalized world. Anderson (2016) made a convincing argument in support of the thesis that the educational future does not belong to developing an increasingly narrowly specialized expertise. He claims that the need that has led to the emergence of such educational offers like TED, the Khan Academy, MIT or Stanford online education is proof that the future is the world of knowledge and people interconnectedness. EXTEND might become a part of this new world making force.

4 Conclusions

Motto "When I entered I knew one world but now I see we must be modern"
(participant's feedback in Dushanbe workshop, Technical University of Tajikistan, June 26, 2019),

The PROSPER project has been our backbone reference in digging up the problematic of post-project implementation. Over a span of one decade, the language teachers involved adopted the communicative approach in language teaching and gradually "humanized" their practice by actually moving in two directions. First, they looked at what **can be done**. In this respect they embraced a certain range of values and the procedures that implement them. Here is a selective list applicable beyond the language class:

- providing the opportunity for choice (subject, time, method) as a path to autonomy;
- meaningfulness through:
 - o real-life-tasks
 - o top-down rather than bottom - up teaching/learning strategy
- authentic inputs
- information gap challenge
- contextualised tasks based on lead-in
- production stages as a way towards meaningfulness
- increased interactivity (pair/group work)
- changed teacher-student roles

Secondly, they looked at what **cannot be done** or the boundaries of change. In this respect, of particular value in the theoretical field have been the authors who embraced a limited paradigm of values and procedures with a long term rippling effect such as Kumaravadivelu, B. *Maximizing Learning potential in the communication classroom* (in Hedge Whithy's *Minimal approach Interaction*, 1996); Jon Taylor in *The Mini- Max Teacher* (2004).

As far as the EXTEND project is concerned, an inspiring answer to the question heading the Dushanbe Workshop was probably given by the Dushanbe workshop participants themselves. When asked *What word do you associate with the EXTEND project?* they answered: *an interesting trip, education, exchange of students between European universities, progress, development, programs, study, qualification, engineering education development, communication, integration, craftsmanship, boost, pedagogy, innovation, I thought about what kind of project it is, "When I entered I knew one world but now I see we must be modern"*. Indeed, a quality dissemination of the kind of the expected gains listed by the Dushanbe participants might ensure its further sustainability alongside with an open mind ready to change, discover and further innovate.

To conclude, the answer to the post-EXTEND future development of the HE Institutions involved lies not only in the hands of the decision makers but mostly in the hands or rather mind and heart of an EXTEND trainee who can find truth in the following statement: *The key to change is having faith that when we get rid of the old, something or someone more magnificent will take its place*" (Levitin, 2014, p. 383).

Table 1. The PROSPER Project in a nutshell

Timeline	1990-1999
Partnership	British Council, UK and the Romanian Ministry of Education
Aim	Upgrading the teaching/learning of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) in Romanian tertiary education
Target	English Departments in five major technical universities and Academy of Economic Studies (initially); English Departments in other economic academies and medical schools
Activities	in-country training courses (1/2 weeks); 10 week training course at the Institute for English Language Education, Lancaster University (78 teachers, 1991-1995); short course training sessions on requested topics; workshops; materials development, test development; course evaluations, course observations, mobilities, newsletter, distance masterships (15 teachers, Manchester University);
Outcomes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 124 teacher trainees from 18 institutions 2. Improved classroom experience 3. Textbooks: English for Science and Technology; English for Business Administration. 4. Newsletter 5. International Conferences: 1993 and 1996 6. Five Language Centres (self-sustainable) 7. Baseline study (in-house) 8. Impact Study (published)

(Source: "Innovation in Teaching English for Specific Purposes in Romania - A Study of Impact" (1999).

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